

REPORT
**KEEP ON
GRAMPING
3.0**

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SOCIETY (ECS) CONFERENCE,
PONTA DELGADA**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Following the success of previous workshops in 2012 and 2019, the *Keep on Gramping 3.0* workshop was held at the 36th European Cetacean Society Conference in Ponta Delgada, Azores, on 12 May 2025. Organized by Arianna Fornaroli (Tethys Research Institute) and Karin Hartman (Nova Atlantis Foundation), the event built on the momentum of past gatherings to assess current knowledge and shape the future of Risso's dolphin (*Grampus griseus*) research, with a focus on the North-East Atlantic Ocean and Mediterranean waters.

Bringing together researchers from diverse geographical regions and career stages, the workshop served as a dynamic platform to exchange recent findings, foster collaboration, and define conservation priorities.

- **Share Recent Research & Build a Knowledge Network**

- Present updates from long-term and recent studies across different regions
- Strengthen connections among Risso's dolphin researchers globally
- Identify emerging trends, knowledge gaps and future research priorities
- Enhance the visibility and cohesion of the Risso's dolphin research community

- **Strengthen Collaboration & Data Sharing**

- Expand and reinforce the Keep on Gramping network
- Harmonize methodologies to support cross-site comparisons
- Encourage joint publications, collaborative proposals, and open data practices
- Support informed decision-making and policy development

- **Advance Conservation Efforts (Focus on North-East Atlantic)**

- Discuss region-specific conservation needs and threats
- Explore the need to revise the IUCN status for Risso's dolphins, especially in the North-East Atlantic
- Support coordinated, science-driven conservation action

WORKSHOP FORMAT

The workshop served as a valuable opportunity for knowledge exchange, collaboration and strategic planning centred on the conservation of Risso's dolphins. The workshop brought together 31 researchers working and adopted a hybrid format for the first time in the Keep On Gramping workshops, with 21 participants attending in person and 10 joining online. The presentations were also fully hybrid: of the 13 speakers, 7 presented in person and 6 online.

It began with a brief welcome and introduction, followed by a series of presentations delivered by researchers from 7 regions in the North-East Atlantic and Mediterranean Sea, each highlighting recent findings and local population trends. The topics covered a wide range of aspects related to Risso's dolphin populations, including abundance and distribution, site fidelity, pathogens and behaviour. These talks offered a comprehensive overview of the current state of research across various study areas.

After a short coffee break, the workshop continued with a dedicated Q&A session, allowing participants to explore the presentations in greater depth.

This was followed by a broader discussion on the IUCN Red List status of Risso's dolphins, with particular focus on the North-East Atlantic populations. Key data requirements and methodological considerations for future IUCN assessments were outlined.

The final session was an open discussion aimed at defining a shared conservation strategy and identifying concrete opportunities for collaboration. The workshop concluded with an agreement to produce a report summarizing observed shifts in population trends, the main outcomes of the event, and recommended next steps to strengthen conservation efforts for Risso's dolphins.

WORKSHOP REPORT

A critical shared outcome that emerged across all presentations was the observation of concerning trends in the studied Risso's dolphin populations. These included signs of population decline, habitat shifts, and ecological changes, issues that raised concern among workshop participants. While the causes of these patterns remain unclear, they underscore the urgency for deeper investigation.

All attendees unanimously agreed on the importance of continuing to monitor their respective study areas and committed to producing a joint output (this report) as a first step toward highlighting the need for enhanced research and conservation action. This collaborative documentation aims to raise awareness of these emerging issues and to advocate for coordinated efforts to understand what is happening to Risso's dolphins across their range.

By fostering scientific dialogue and cooperation, Keep on Gramping 3.0 reaffirmed its central role in building a unified research front for Risso's dolphin conservation, rooted in long-term monitoring, knowledge exchange, and joint action

SESSION 1. PROJECT PRESENTATIONS

Long term studies of Risso's dolphins off Pico island

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A population of Risso's dolphins (*Grampus griseus*), has been monitored since 2000 by the Nova Atlantis Foundation, off Pico Island. Over the long-term, 1700 individuals have been identified and several ecological features of this population have been published. Risso's dolphins in the Azores maintain a unique social structure with adult males living in stable clusters and female temporally forming stable nurseries. Sub-adults hang out in more weakly associated bachelor groups. Calving season is taking place between June and August, and females with calves use the coastal waters for nursing, where stable male clusters are guarding the area to enhance reproduction success, in restricted home ranges. In addition, around 250 animals are resident in the research area of approximately 500 km². This population is sensitive to anthropogenic pressure and shifts its resting hours during high season towards midday, when low or non-whale watch activity is taking place. Disturbance of the delicate resting hours for sensitive groups like females with new-borns and older calves may have consequences for the reproductive success of a population in the long-term. In a recent analysis, a decline in Risso's dolphin presence has been detected compared to an increase in pilot whale presence. These trends seem to correlate with the rising sea temperatures e.g. climate change. The decline has also been observed when looking at the number of groups, unique individual's and the variety among groups that have been encountered and identified at sea. In addition, groups with nurseries and sub-adults are being sighted less. There is a worrying decline in the number of new-borns counted, including 2 seasons with no new-borns observed (2020 and 2023).

Mediterranean Risso' Dolphin: Conservation Status, Strategies and Challenges between Research and Management

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Intensive monitoring efforts conducted on various scales (regional, subregional and local) in the Mediterranean Sea have, in last decade, led to significant progress in the understanding of the distribution and abundance of the Mediterranean subpopulation of Risso's dolphins, as well as the threats affecting the species. The collaborative effort in discussing the new evidence during international workshops and working groups allowed the reassessment of the Conservation Status of the species in 2022 and the development of a Conservation Management Plan identifying priority actions and mitigation measures for its conservation.

Currently, the Risso's dolphin Mediterranean subpopulation is assessed in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, as Endangered (A2bc) based on an inferred linear reduction in population size of more than 80% over a three-generation period. In addition, a 50% reduction in its Area of Occupancy (AOO), add a further point of concerns. The causes of the inferred reduction in Risso's dolphin population and range, remain unclear. Currently main threats, include bycatch in offshore gillnets, pelagic longlines, and other fishing gear. While it is possible that inferred declines could result from fishing mortality alone, other threats, including competition with fisheries and habitat degradation, are likely contributors.

A Conservation Management Plan (CMP) for the species has been developed within the framework of ACCOBAMS to stimulate and guide conservation. The goal is to manage human activities that affect this species in the Mediterranean Sea so as to maintain a favourable conservation status throughout their historical range, based on the best available scientific knowledge. The plan identifies bycatch in fishing nets and disturbance from impulsive/acute noise resulting from industrial and military activities as priority threats. Research aimed at improving knowledge of the species' temporal and spatial distribution, habitat use and stranding data analysis are among the most feasible research activities for providing adequate management advice. Wider adoption and implementation of guidelines and resolutions (such as those of the IWC, ACCOBAMS and CMS) is a priority in order to mitigate the adverse impact of human activities on Risso's dolphins. Finally, the development or support

of long-term monitoring activities should be considered a priority for effective species conservation.

Programmes like 'LIFE' project, aimed at supporting and further developing the surveillance of the conservation status of species covered by the HABITAT DIRECTIVE (Annex II-IV) are among the examples of collaborative efforts to improve the knowledge on endangered species distribution and habitat use. The results emerged by the LIFE CONCEPTU Maris (<https://www.lifeconceptu.eu/en/>), a subregional scale project focused on filling current gaps by collecting data along fixed transects, revealed a significant shift in the species' predicted ecological range, seasonal flexibility, and a substantial lack of protection within species' current distribution area.

Site fidelity and connectivity of Risso's Dolphins in the English Channel: importance of coastal habitat and migration patterns

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The EDRIM Project, led by AL LARK Association, focuses on studying and protecting Risso's dolphins in the English Channel. The project explores the dolphins' site fidelity, distribution, and trophic ecology to inform conservation efforts. A key part of the project is a PhD thesis, conducted in collaboration with the University of La Rochelle and Pelagis, structured across three years, each focusing on a different aspect of dolphin ecology. The first year examines site fidelity in French Brittany using photo-identification and capture-recapture models. Data from two regions, North East French Brittany (NEFB) and North West French Brittany (NWFB), are being analysed. Early findings show seasonal fidelity at NEFB, possibly linked to feeding or calving patterns, while NWFB appears to serve as a transit zone. The second year will focus on the distribution of Risso's dolphins along the Atlantic coast using species distribution modeling (SDM), considering environmental factors and human impacts such as prey availability and boat traffic. The third year will analyse the dolphins' trophic ecology, studying stable isotopes and contaminants in stranded samples (liver, muscle, kidney, blubber) to understand diet, habitat use, and exposure to pollutants at an individual level. Although we are working with limited data, the collaboration between researchers, marine conservation managers, and citizen volunteers is crucial. We hope this research will offer valuable insights for the conservation of Risso's dolphins, contributing to a better future for this species.

General overview and habitat preference of Risso's dolphins off the south coast of Portugal

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Even though sightings of Risso's dolphins (*Grampus griseus*) off southern Portugal are infrequent, ongoing long-term data collection grants insights into their ecology, behaviour, and occurrence. Boat-based opportunistic and dedicated marine megafauna surveys have been carried out since 2010 and 2015 respectively. A total of 84 Risso's dolphin sightings were recorded between 2010 and 2024. The main behavioural activity was travelling (48.9%), followed by un-identified behaviour (21.6%), socialising (14.8%), feeding and foraging (11.4%), and resting (3.4%). Foraging-associated behaviour such as torpedo-dives were also recorded. Both sexes and all age classes have been observed. Photo-identification revealed the presence of 164 individuals with a re-sighting rate of 33.5% (n = 55 animals). There may be a certain spatial division between the areas off Sagres and Albufeira with only four individuals documented in both areas. To investigate how dynamic and static oceanographic variables influence Risso's dolphin occurrence and habitat preference, presence-absence models were used. Risso's dolphin presence was recorded on 63 occasions with an average group size of 10 animals (range: 1 to 45 dolphins) and a presence of immature animals in most groups (73.0%). Generalised Additive Models were fitted and the optimal model showed that Risso's dolphins' probability of occurrence was higher close to the coast, and positively related to sea surface temperature, reaching a maximum presence probability between 22°C and 24°C. A positive but nonsignificant relationship with one-month time lagged chlorophyll-a concentration was also detected. The high calf presence may partially drive this distribution with warmer waters being suitable for offspring and areas closer to the coast granting predator protection and allowing shallower foraging for lactating females. Future investigations in the south of Portugal may focus on Risso's dolphin seasonality, behaviour, anthropogenic impacts, group types (i.e., nursery/male/bachelor groups), and sharing photo-identification catalogues to gain a better understanding of their spatial range.

Risso's dolphin site fidelity off the Catalan coast and movements across the Balearic Sea

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Knowledge of the distribution of species provides essential baseline information for their conservation and for the management of human activities that may affect them. Identifying areas within their range to which individuals regularly return can reveal patterns of site fidelity. This is particularly important for species such as Risso's dolphin (*Grampus griseus*), for which such information remains scarce in the Mediterranean. On the one hand, photo-identification surveys were used to study the patterns of site fidelity along the Garraf underwater canyon system (NW Mediterranean Sea). Data was collected along 237 boat surveys between 2017 and 2023, resulting in 56 sightings and 303 different individuals identified. Site fidelity was assessed using eight Site Fidelity Indices (SFI) derived from indicators of permanence and periodicity. Divisive hierarchical clustering analysis was used to classify recaptured individuals into three groups: seasonal residents (40 individuals), regular visitors (70 individuals) and occasional visitors (6 individuals). The 187 individuals sighted only once were considered transient. On the other hand, a collaboration between eight organisations (six in Catalonia and two in the Balearic Islands) allowed for the comparison of their photo-identification catalogues. Data were collected between 2010 and 2024, resulting in 101 sightings and the identification of 756 unique individuals. In total, 76 recaptures were identified: five individuals seen by three organisations and 71 by two. Short-distance and medium-distance movements were detected along the Catalan coast and Balearic Islands, but there were no recaptures between these two regions. The results highlight the importance of the Garraf Canyon system as a relevant habitat for certain individuals, as well as the regional mobility of the species. This study highlights the need to further expand photo-identification efforts at the Mediterranean scale in order to better understand the distribution patterns and habitat use of Risso's dolphins in a broader ecological context.

Updates on Risso's dolphins in the Pelagos Sanctuary: Re-sightings and movements

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The Risso's dolphin (*Grampus griseus*) has historically been observed in the Pelagos Sanctuary, particularly in its northwestern portion. In the 1990s and 2000s, a resident population of approximately 100 individuals was regularly sighted in the area. In recent years, however, the situation has changed dramatically. Since 2010, sightings have declined to the point of near disappearance. The causes of this decrease are still unclear: they may include changes in primary marine productivity, competition with other species, and a general decline in prey availability.

Over more than two decades (1990-2014), almost 300 individuals were photo-identified by the Tethys Research Institute in the northwestern portion of the Pelagos Sanctuary. After five years without sightings in the study area, 38 Risso's dolphins were photo-identified between 2020 and 2024. Of these, only four individuals (10,5%) had previously been photo-identified in the study area. Meanwhile, in the Gulf of Genoa, in 2013, 95 individuals were photo-identified, with few matches compared to the historical Tethys catalogue.

The InterMed project brought together several research institutions from the Mediterranean Sea, creating a large shared photographic archive of a total of 635 different individuals and revealing 155 matches, but only from contiguous geographic areas, and two distinct geographical units: Ligurian Sea and Campanian Archipelago (Italy).

Data from the ACCOBAMS Survey Initiative (ASI, 2018–2019) indicated a preference of Risso's dolphins for the western Mediterranean, with higher encounter rates in the Alborán Sea, along the Algerian coast, and around the Balearic Islands. Moreover, sightings occurred further offshore, in pelagic habitats, compared to previous reports in the literature.

In conclusion, the data collected in recent years indicate that the population of Risso's dolphins in the Pelagos Sanctuary has undergone a drastic decline, while some individuals have moved towards other areas. The future of research will be to expand the collaboration network between institutions, thanks also to projects such as PROMED (2024–2026), to better understand the dynamics of this species in the Mediterranean.

Risso's dolphins off the west coast of Scotland

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There is a limited understanding of Risso's dolphin population structure in the north Atlantic and whilst the species is considered widely distributed within Scottish waters, there is currently a lack of data to determine sub-populations. As a result, no separate regional abundance estimates have been made and subsequently, in UK waters, all Risso's dolphins are encompassed within a single Management Unit (MU) however, this assumption has been made based on a lack of evidence proving otherwise (IAMMWG, 2023). Improved knowledge of spatial and temporal movements of individual Risso's dolphins can provide further insights into the importance of specific habitats and ensure appropriate measures are implemented for the long-term monitoring and protection of Risso's dolphins in Scottish (and wider UK) waters. In recent years there have been some major advancements in our understanding of the Risso's that use Scottish (and wider UK) waters. Some initial steps have been taken towards their protection, including the designation of the first ever Marine Protected Area (MPA) for Risso's dolphins off the northeast coast of the Isle of Lewis in the Outer Hebrides. Comparatively, research has also demonstrated the potential importance of inshore coastal waters in northeast Scotland, Orkney, and Shetland as critical habitat for Risso's dolphins with individuals showing both intra-and inter annual site-fidelity. More recently, an analysis of all available photographs of Risso's dolphins taken off the west coast of Scotland and the creation of the 'West Coast of Scotland Risso's dolphin photo-id catalogue' and associated database, is providing evidence which supports preliminary indications of habitat and site preferences for individual dolphins and provides evidence of behavioural sub-structuring within Risso's populations in UK. This evidence will be important justification to the UK Government for the recognition of at least one distinct management unit of Risso's dolphins in Scotland.

Risso's dolphins in northern Norway

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The distribution range of the Risso's dolphin (*Grampus griseus*) in the Northeast Atlantic is described as far north as the north of Scotland and almost reaching the south of the Faroe Islands. Occasional sightings have been documented in regions further north too, but it seems like these are movements out of the species' distribution range rather than part of it. The whale watching company Whale2Sea and the research organisation Norwegian Orca Survey, both operating from Andenes, northern Norway (~69°N), have documented Risso's dolphins in Bleik Canyon every summer since 2017. Number of encounters per year increased from one encounter in 2017, 2018, and 2019 to 2 days in 2020, 4 days in 2021, 6 days in 2022, and 19 days in 2023, before a decline to 12 days in 2024. Photo-identification shows that number of individuals in the area increased likewise. Between 2017 and 2024, 104 different individuals were identified and re-sightings of individuals over different years show that at least some individuals returned to Bleik Canyon in different years. 8 individuals were documented in two different years and 2 individuals in three different years. Groups are composed of different age classes and both sexes, including mother-calf-pairs, juveniles, and adult males. These findings show that Bleik Canyon has become part of the species' distribution range in summer. Increasing Risso's dolphins presence in the Bleik Canyon area is most likely linked to increasing water temperatures in the Northeast Atlantic but was possibly accelerated by other additional factors.

Building bridges for Risso's Dolphins conservation, Reflections through the EDRIM project

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Risso's dolphin conservation in the English Channel and French Brittany faces major challenges: limited sightings, fragmented data and uncoordinated efforts. The EDRIM project, led by AL LARK association, emerges to address these gaps by fostering collaboration among researchers and organizations across regions. The project has evolved from informal meetings into a growing network exchanging photo-ID catalogues, methodologies and tools. Despite challenges such as limited resources and data governance issues, EDRIM propose concrete steps to strengthen cooperation. This presentation outlines the project's progress, challenges and vision.

Pathogens-microbiome interaction in Risso's dolphins: preliminary insights

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Cetaceans play an important role in the marine ecosystem as apex predators, secondary consumers, and indicators of ocean health. Despite their importance, human activities have significantly endangered many cetacean species, through hunting, overfishing, and environmental exploitation. Although conservation efforts have helped some species recover, many remain endangered or vulnerable. Cetaceans-associated microbial communities play critical roles in host nutrition, differentiation of host tissues, colonization resistance and the development of immune function, as well as other beneficial processes. Studies of faecal specimens from several cetacean's species have shown a striking degree of host specificity of microbiota, reflecting the influence of host phylogeny, gut anatomy, diet or infectious diseases. Despite a growing understanding of the factors that shape the structure and function of the microbiotas of some species, little is known relative to the Risso's dolphin. Here we report the gut microbiome profile and the occurrence of human-transmitted protozoan parasite *Cryptosporidium parvum* in the faecal samples of one wild Risso's dolphin living in the Gulf of Taranto, Ionian Sea, that represents an area highly anthropized within the Mediterranean Basin. A predominance of *Clostridiaceae* family associated to zoonotic form of *C. parvum* was reported, possibly reflecting an unhealthy status related to the anthropic pressure. These preliminary results shed light on the importance of studying the microbiotas and pathogens-related of cetaceans, especially in species living in areas with intense human activities, to better understand the factors linked to their health status in an effort to link the biodiversity and conservation of a species.

Social association of Risso's dolphins in the Ligurian Sea (North-Western Mediterranean Sea): Insights from long-term photo-ID data.

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This study investigates the social structure of Risso's dolphins (*Grampus griseus*) in the Ligurian Sea, within the Pelagos Sanctuary. Using photo-identification data collected by the Tethys Research Institute from 1990 to 2013, we analysed association patterns among 81 highly marked individuals, each observed at least four times during 101 sightings. Individuals were categorized as adult females (AF: 27%) or of unknown sex (US: 73%) based on calf association criteria, with calves excluded from the analysis to avoid potential bias. The Half-Weight Association Index (HWI) was applied to assess social relationships and analysed through SOCPROG 2.9. Our results revealed a well-differentiated social structure ($S = 0.65$, $SE = 0.04$, $n = 100$ bootstrap replicates) without any segregation of units ($Q = 0.216$). The average HWI (HWI_{ave}) across all individuals was 0.10 ± 0.03 , indicating low overall association levels, whereas the mean maximum HWI (HWI_{max}) reached 0.54 ± 0.15 , with 19% of individuals showing $HWI_{max} \geq 0.70$. Notably, individuals in the US category exhibited a higher HWI_{max} (0.55 ± 0.15) compared to AF (0.40 ± 0.12). The best-fitting model for the Standardized Lagged Association Rate (SLAR) identified Two levels of casual acquaintances, reflecting both short-term and longer-term associations. Permutation tests highlighted that the social structure was mainly influenced by short-term relationships ($n = 10,000$, $flips = 1000$, $p < 0.05$). However, some individuals formed longer-term associations, as demonstrated by two likely adult males consistently observed together from 1991 to 2005 (HWI_{ave} = 0.91), indicating a stable association. Our findings suggest a social structure characterised by fluid interactions and preferred, long-lasting associations, as observed in other regions. This research offers interesting insights into the social dynamics of the Mediterranean subpopulation of *Grampus griseus*, recently listed as Endangered on the IUCN Red List, underscoring the urgency for further studies to support conservation efforts.

SESSION 2. GENERAL DISCUSSION

Q&A SESSION

The Q&A session following the presentations highlighted the need for collaboration and localised approaches to conservation.

- Marianna asked Oihana whether any pathogen analyses were conducted on the stranded Risso's dolphin samples included in her PhD research (see abstract page 8). Oihana replied that, at present, the focus of her study is mainly on trophic ecology, and no pathogen analyses are underway. However, she expressed openness to potential collaborations on this aspect.
- Josh asked Caterina Lanfredi and Sabina Airoidi about the increase in Risso's dolphin group size observed in spring in the North-Eastern Mediterranean, and whether it might relate to mating behaviour or prey availability. Caterina replied that this pattern is likely influenced by the availability and distribution of data in the area, though ecological factors cannot be excluded.
- Oihana raised a question about the use of Bayesian modelling to estimate population size when data are sparse and sample sizes are low. She asked whether colleagues had experience applying similar frameworks and whether any posterior survival estimates for adult or juvenile Risso's dolphins existed. As no one was able to provide an answer during the discussion, she highlighted that this gap should be highlighted, as it reflects the current lack of survival estimates for the species at the European scale.
- Mark Simmonds raised two key points that led to important follow-up questions:
 1. Based on the presentations (especially Nicola's, which showed clear spatial segregation even within the same region, see abstract page 12), Risso's dolphins appear to consist of distinct segregated populations. These populations may require targeted, localised protection.

2. He inquired about the IUCN Red List process, asking how to move forward with formalising conservation assessments.

These topics will be addressed in detail in the following session.

- Susana asked Alexander whether the apparent increase in Risso's dolphin sightings in his study area in Norway could be explained by a rise in observation effort (see abstract page 13). Alexander acknowledged the difficulty of quantifying effort in the region but confirmed that vessel traffic has increased in recent years. Still, he noted that since 2017, Risso's dolphins have been sighted every summer, suggesting that the increase in sightings is not solely due to increased effort or boat presence.
- Caterina emphasised the significant growth in knowledge over the past two decades, partly thanks to broader tools like citizen science and whale-watching platforms. She stressed that although the efforts are often small-scale, when combined, they enhance our understanding and must be shared collectively to effectively inform conservation strategies.
- Ing asked Karin about upwelling dynamics south of Pico Island since 2016, and whether reduced prey availability could be linked to the observed decline in Risso's dolphin sightings. Karin responded that while she cannot confirm this definitively, it could be possible. However, the dolphins are still present in the area, though they are being seen less frequently.
- Miguel asked about prey-detection distance by echolocation and whether any detailed studies existed on Risso's dolphins stealing bait from artisanal squid-fishing boats, especially in Italy. Sabina confirmed that such interactions have been observed off the coast of Punta Campanella (Campania, Italy), though she is not aware of any formal publications, only personal communication. Similar interactions have also been noted in southern Sardinia.
- Juliette asked Alexander what might explain the unusually high number of Risso's dolphins recorded in 2023. Alexander noted that it was his first year on the project and that requesting additional photos from local contributors may have increased the number of identified individuals, though he could not confirm whether ecological or environmental factors were also involved.
- Beatriz asked the group whether the mixed-species sightings of Risso's dolphins, particularly with striped and common dolphins as observed in the Aegean Sea, were common in other regions, and whether any acoustic data were available.
 - Antonella reported sightings with bottlenose dolphins around Sardinia.

- Alicia mentioned occasional sightings with common dolphins in Portugal.
- Nicola observed frequent associations with bottlenose dolphins in her study area and noted increased reports of hybridisation. Interactions are usually friendly, but aggressive encounters can also occur. The behaviour does not appear to be influenced by competition for food, since the two species target different prey species and have different diets.
- Finally, Antonella offered a thoughtful reflection: almost all the studies presented showed some level of change (whether in abundance, habitat use, or spatial distribution) highlighting how dynamic and vulnerable these populations are. She emphasized that even sightings of Risso's dolphins in new areas, such as Norway, could be valuable. Across the presentations, it became clear that different social groups have different habitat requirements, which has major implications for conservation. We cannot rely solely on broad habitat protection; instead, we need a more fine-scale approach. Protecting the species as a whole requires understanding and conserving these distinct local populations.

The final takeaway was a shared sense that while the collaboration across different regions and research groups is incredibly valuable, there is a need to make it more structured and coordinated to maximize its impact on Risso's dolphin conservation. The collaboration among us is beautiful, but from now on it needs to be structured.

IUCN ASSESSMENT: CAN WE ADVOCATE AN IUCN REASSESSMENT FOR THE NORTH-EAST ATLANTIC?

During the workshop it was discussed whether a proposal for a new IUCN assessment could be produced for the North-East Atlantic, taking into account the previous information.

As part of the workshop, members of the “Grampus group” (Caterina Lanfredi, Lea David, and Antonella Arcangeli) presented the results of a comprehensive assessment of the Risso’s Dolphin in the Mediterranean Sea (see abstract page 6). Their contribution provided valuable insight into the methodologies and findings of the most recent IUCN Red List evaluations, highlighting key distinctions between the Mediterranean and Atlantic populations.

*The Mediterranean subpopulation of Risso’s Dolphin has been assessed separately due to evidence of genetic differentiation from Atlantic populations. The IUCN Red List assessment of 2022 lists this subpopulation as Endangered under criteria A2bc. Mitochondrial DNA studies have demonstrated a clear genetic distinction between dolphins in the Mediterranean and those in the Azores, the UK, and other Atlantic regions, supporting the classification of the Mediterranean group as a distinct subpopulation. While data on abundance and distribution have improved, assessing subpopulation size at the basin scale remains challenging. Long-term monitoring efforts in the Ligurian-Corso-Provençal basin, one of the most intensively studied areas, have documented a reduction of over 50% in individual numbers over a 10-year period. This trend supports a projected decline exceeding 80% over three generations, which would be consistent with a Critically Endangered status. Although this estimate is based on a relatively small portion of the Mediterranean subpopulation, the widespread nature of the likely drivers (particularly interactions with fisheries) suggests that similar declines may be occurring elsewhere. Giving the high level of uncertainties to infer decline from a localised studies and apply it to the regional scale, the large extent of the area considered in the assessment, the high uncertainties in the threats and levels of pressure affecting the subpopulation over different areas of the Mediterranean, the **Endangered** (A2bc) category is considered more appropriate for the species than Critically Endangered.*

*At the European level, the species was last assessed in 2022 and is currently listed as Least Concern. This classification reflects the availability of recent regional abundance data, such as the SCANS-III survey (2016), and the ACCOBAMS Survey Initiative (2018). Despite this progress, significant knowledge gaps remain, particularly in areas like Macaronesia and the southern Mediterranean. Additionally, while several threats have been identified, such as bycatch, overfishing, underwater noise, marine debris, and chemical pollutants, their impact on population dynamics remains **poorly understood**. The relative rarity of documented bycatch events, possibly linked to the species' offshore distribution, further complicates efforts to assess risk at a population level.*

The most recent European-level reassessment of Risso's dolphin was published in 2022. This assessment is at European level, including both the North-East Atlantic and the Mediterranean Sea, as defined by the IUCN's current regional framework. However, while the Mediterranean subpopulation has already been evaluated independently through the regional assessment, the North-East Atlantic does not yet have such a designation. The first step toward improving conservation efforts in this area would be to consult with IUCN authorities to clarify the current delineation of assessment regions and explore the possibility of recognizing the North-East Atlantic as a separate assessment unit. Should this regional categorisation be approved, the next step would be to examine which IUCN Red List criteria could support a change in conservation status for the North-East Atlantic population.

Caterina briefly described the methodology used for the Mediterranean assessment. This process involved the integration of data from multiple monitoring platforms (see abstract page 6), covering a large portion of the basin. Although it did not include the entire Mediterranean, the effort represented a substantial advance in spatial coverage. However, applying the IUCN Red List criteria was highly complex due to data heterogeneity and gaps.

Mark Simmonds emphasised that the populations across different regions are clearly distinct and merit tailored conservation measures. While the IUCN process is one possible route, it is not the only framework available. He stressed the importance of documenting and publishing findings, clearly demonstrating that these populations are both unique and subject to significant changes in distribution and abundance.

Nicola added that the current European assessment can be misleading, as it includes the entire Mediterranean Sea, even though the Mediterranean subpopulation has a separate evaluation. She also highlighted significant inconsistencies in the reported distribution of Risso's dolphins. For example, data presented by Alexander reveal that the distribution map included in the IUCN assessment does not reflect current observations, which show notable range shifts and new areas of occurrence (in Norway, for example).

In the UK and elsewhere in the North-East Atlantic, there is evidence of population segregation. These observations point to the need for increased coordination among researchers working in the region. Given the apparent changes in distribution and indications of local declines, there is an urgent need to move beyond the current Least Concern classification at the European level and adopt a more region-specific approach.

Antonella concluded that a key outcome of this workshop should be the development of a comprehensive, collaborative report summarizing the current state of knowledge on Risso's dolphins in the North-East Atlantic. Such a report could serve as a foundation for engaging with the IUCN and other relevant bodies to initiate a reassessment process. Despite the current Least Concern status, mounting evidence of population shifts and local declines suggests that conservation action is needed now.

Summarizing the outcome about IUCN Assessment feasibility in NE Atlantic:

- There is a marked contrast between the Mediterranean and North-East Atlantic in terms of assessment feasibility:
 - The Mediterranean subpopulation is genetically distinct, justifying its separate assessment.
 - The North-East Atlantic population is more segregated, with some subpopulations showing the presence of both resident and transient individuals (see abstracts pp. 5, 7, 8, 11).
- For these reasons, currently the NE Atlantic can't be considered a unified assessment unit since it's not included in one of the regions identified by the IUCN (consulting the official IUCN website at the moment of the workshop).
- A regional assessment would require:
 - Formal approval from IUCN central authorities.
 - Harmonization of ecological and genetic data across the region.

CONSERVATION OUTCOMES

While the IUCN assessment process is an important tool for advancing conservation, it is not the only available tool. Antonella emphasised that, particularly within the European context, other legal and policy instruments could be exploited to support conservation efforts for Risso's dolphins in the North-East Atlantic. These include:

- The EU Habitats Directive
- The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)
- The Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework

IUCN assessments, in contrast, although recognised globally, are not legally binding. Antonella suggested that a targeted LIFE project could be a valuable next step to promote conservation actions specifically for this species, noting that the current call for proposals is open.

Joana added that in the Azores, work is ongoing under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, but the current reported status of Risso's dolphins is "unknown." While this reflects a lack of data, it could also provide an opportunity to justify the need for a LIFE project focused on improving knowledge and conservation outcomes.

Caterina reiterated the significance of IUCN assessments, citing examples from the Mediterranean Sea where genetic differentiation justified the recognition of subpopulations in recent evaluations: long-finned pilot whales in the Strait of Gibraltar, killer whales in the Strait of Gibraltar, striped dolphins in the Gulf of Corinth, bottlenose dolphins in the Mediterranean. She agreed that the European-level assessment rightly includes the Mediterranean Sea, as IUCN assessments are conducted at a broad regional scale. However, she also stressed the need to ask: how segregated are these populations in reality? And more specifically, how genetically distinct are they from one another?

To address these questions, Lucrezia presented her PhD research, which focuses on comparing the genetic profiles of Mediterranean and Atlantic populations using both mitochondrial and nuclear DNA markers. Her work includes historical samples from both regions, and she will soon incorporate data from the UK to further explore population structure and connectivity.

Finally, Karin emphasized the importance of maintaining collaboration among researchers and continuing to share knowledge. She also underlined the value of compiling a comprehensive report following this workshop to guide next steps and strengthen future conservation initiatives.

CONCLUSIONS

With Keep On Gramping 3.0, we aim to follow in the footsteps of the dedicated researchers and conservationists who laid the groundwork in the first two editions. Building on their efforts to identify knowledge gaps, promote collaboration, and push for stronger conservation actions, this third workshop seeks to continue the momentum. By bringing together researchers from different study areas and fostering open exchange, we hope to reinforce the collaborative spirit of the KOG community and contribute to the long-term protection of Risso's dolphins, especially in key regions such as the Azores.

The first Keep On Gramping workshop (ECS 2012, Galway) laid the foundations for a collaborative network of researchers studying Risso's dolphins. It highlighted key knowledge gaps and conservation concerns, including their patchy distribution, unique social structure, small local populations, and vulnerability to anthropogenic impacts (particularly noise pollution and bycatch). The workshop called for:

- Precautionary conservation measures in areas of regular occurrence,
- Long-term photo-ID and genetic studies to define management units,
- The use of complementary techniques (e.g., acoustics, stable isotopes),
- Systematic surveys and habitat modelling to identify hotspots,
- The establishment of marine protected areas.

The second edition (Keep On Gramping 2.0) took place at the WMMC in 2019 (Barcelona), with the primary goal of strengthening the KOG community and sharing updated findings. It focused on building infrastructure for collaboration and data sharing, including:

- A call for standardized photo-ID databases,
- Creation of a social media presence and publication repository,
- Promotion of inter-site researcher exchanges,
- A proposal to reassess the global and Mediterranean IUCN status of the species, leveraging expert knowledge and coordinated action to push for a review.

In its third edition, Keep On Gramping 3.0 aimed to bring together experienced researchers with long-standing knowledge of the species and younger researchers presenting up-to-date results from different study areas, fostering continuity in Risso's dolphin research.

Collaboration is essential: not just as a matter of projects or programs, but as a matter of people. Caterina, Lea, and Antonella provided a compelling example of this during their presentation. At first glance, their work appeared as three separate initiatives: the IUCN Red Listing process, the ACCOBAMS initiative, and the LIFE project under the EU Habitats Directive. However, they made a significant effort to cooperate and align their goals. Turning data into effective conservation projects is not always easy. As Antonella Arcangeli emphasized, true collaboration, particularly when aiming to develop a LIFE project, requires:

- Standardized data collection
- Standardized data management
- Standardized data analysis
- Translating scientific findings into formats accessible and actionable for policymakers

The presentations collectively highlighted a concerning trend: changes in the spatial distribution and social dynamics of Risso's dolphins are becoming increasingly evident across various study regions.

In the Azores, where Risso's dolphins have been studied intensively for over 25 years, Karin's presentation highlighted recent observations that suggest a shift in population dynamics. First, a decline in group diversity has been reported, with social units appearing less varied, reflecting shifts in individual movement patterns. Second, there is a measurable reduction in the number of calves observed per year in the study area, suggesting a potential drop in reproductive success. Perhaps most striking is the reduced occurrence of nursery groups, that might indicate habitat degradation or a behavioural response to changing conditions, such as increased boat traffic, shifts in prey distribution, or climatic anomalies.

In the Mediterranean Sea, the species appears to be shifting its habitat. This is evident not only in localised areas, such as the declining encounter rate in the Pelagos Sanctuary, as highlighted by Caterina and Sabina, but also across broader regions. Although the overall range remains similar, the dolphins seem to be selecting different habitats, likely influenced by several factors, including distance from submarine canyons and variations in water productivity. These changes may be driven by climate change and increasing anthropogenic pressure.

Recent observations indicate a northward expansion of the Risso's dolphin distribution range in the Northeast Atlantic. In his presentation, Alexander illustrated how encounters in northern Norway (~69°N), a region previously considered outside the species' typical range, have become increasingly regular in recent years. This emerging pattern is likely linked to rising sea temperatures in the Northeast Atlantic, possibly accelerated by additional environmental or ecological factors. Similar distributional shifts were observed in other regions discussed during the workshop, highlighting a broader trend of habitat changes affecting the species.

This workshop facilitated the presentation of further evidence relating to the Risso's dolphin occurrence in the North-East Atlantic and Mediterranean Sea. All of which are crucial to know for there to be an effective conservation of the species:

- Most of the populations studied and presented during the workshop are facing a shift in distribution and a decreasing in their historical habitat.
- The population is fragmented.
- The species shows an internal social segregation that reflects in different habitat preferences for different social groups. It would not be effective protecting only a general habitat without taking into account these differences.

PARTICIPANTS

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- ~ Karin Hartman, Nova Atlantis Foundation

Participants

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- ~ Eleonora Barbaccia, Politecnico di Milano
- ~ Miguel Barreto
- ~ Juliette Biacchi, Association AL LARK
- ~ Ing Chen
- ~ Lea David, ACCOBAMS Scientific Committee member and task manager on marine protected area
- ~ Lorenzo Di Cerbo, Università di Genova
- ~ Alexander Eckerle, University of Bergen, Norway
- ~ Tom Felce, Manx Whale and Dolphin Watch
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